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Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind

Md. Anowar Hossain

Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023

(engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

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Profile of Professor (Dr.) Anowar Hossain

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Principle of knowledge industry

To serve the society in a right direction and right purpose of PhD education for the right peace of Mankind when Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain faced life-threatening conspiracy to pursue his PhD at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University (Hossain, 2023d, 2023e, 2023an, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023bf) (Hossain, 2023am, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bh, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bo, 2023bt, 2023bu).

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Introductory statements

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world. Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has an expertise on PhD supervision who can teach a PhD researcher by a very limited time for achieving PhD degree without harassment. Dr. Anowar Hossain has authorization to supervise PhD researchers in different countries like Bangladesh, India, China, Australia, UK, USA, Romania and many other countries all over the world. He has long terms experiences dealing with critical professors, critical PhD situations in home and abroad. He, Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has a laboratory platform in RMIT University, Australia; University of Calcutta, India; Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh; City University, Bangladesh. Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain has achievements and sole author contributions for PhD education (**M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018**) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; Hossain & Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015, 2019a, 2019c; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023b, 2023al, 2023br; Hossain et al.; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2019; Samanta et al., 2016) (**Hossain, 2023ag, 2023ak, 2023be, 2023bq, 2023bs**) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023f, 2023g, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023ar, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bm, 2023bn, 2023bp, 2023bq, 2023bs, 2023bt, 2023bu)

He is inviting PhD researcher for PhD supervision on

- ✓ PhD in Textile Engineering
- ✓ PhD in Textile Coloration
- ✓ PhD in Technical Textiles
- ✓ PhD in Defence Textiles
- ✓ PhD in Geo-textiles
- ✓ PhD in Chemical Engineering
- ✓ PhD in Fashion & Textiles

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- ✓ PhD in Criminology
- ✓ PhD in Social Crime Management
- ✓ PhD in Assessment Standardization in Education

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is also inviting PhD researcher for PhD supervision in different background of candidate to make right PhD alignment (under consultation).

Table 1, PhD Structure

Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023	One Year Duration PhD	Tuition fees (Structure ongoing) 20000USD for one-time payment
University Affiliation	Two/three years duration PhD	Scholarship/Self-finance

Education Qualification of PhD candidate (Structure ongoing)

BSc in Engineering/MSc in Engineering/MA/MPhil with excellent academic background depending on academic and professional practices

Researcher versus teaching experiences

In general, teaching experiences denotes delivery of existing knowledge of specific subject when research experience denotes the creation of new knowledge and delivery of new knowledge for the peace of mankind. A researcher can think every solution in better way and better way, exceptional way and exceptional way, winning way and winning way than other people. A primary school teacher teaches the students who is not a researcher, a high school teacher teaches the students who is not a researcher, a university teacher teaches the students who is not a researcher. Every teacher is not a researcher but every researcher is a teacher for global peace of mankind if he can contribute honestly.

Researcher versus professional experiences

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A professional engineer, medical practitioner, lawyer, government and non-government job holders who are determined, they can improve their professional performance capability through PhD education. A PhD researcher is always respected all over the world for his performance and right-thinking capability for self-development for the peace of mankind. For example, a professional engineer may have seventy to eighty years experience who cannot think/solve like a researcher for professional solution and/or professional climbing. There is huge lacking of right PhD schooling all over the world when

- ✓ PhD research is not for a promotion
- ✓ PhD research is not for a publication
- ✓ PhD research is not for writing Dr. before the name
- ✓ PhD research is a matter of human growth for critical solution in the way simplicity and originality
- ✓ PhD research is a professional training for life time progression
- ✓ PhD research is a flavour of whole mankind all over the world
- ✓ PhD research has no ending point, it is so tough to certify for completion of PhD research
- ✓ University timeframe of a PhD research is a very starting point of a PhD researcher

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